
USE OF RESOURCES AND SERVICES IN RAYAT SHIKSHAN SANTHA'S
AUTONOMOUS COLLEGES IN SATARA CITY: A COMPARATIVE
STUDY

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Abstract:

Users' capacity to utilise library resources and services effectively depends on the availability of necessary reading materials, including books, while college libraries also need to offer users cutting-edge, need-based library services to meet their academic and learning needs. This study's main goals are to understand why users use libraries, examine the resources offered there, and identify the products and services that people most frequently utilise. The researcher employed a questionnaire and survey approach as a tool to gather primary data from the users' community for this investigation.

Keywords: *Library resources, Library service, Users satisfaction.*

Introduction:

A person's evolution into a superior intellectual with increased consciousness and spiritual awareness is seen as being facilitated by education. The process of learning at the university level is an essential part of human growth on a global scale. In addition to providing high level skills for every job market, college education also trains people.

The idea behind a library and its services is to offer support to customers regardless of caste, creed, gender, or colour. The establishment of social justice took place in libraries. Any academic institution's library serves as its beating heart, drawing users there to pursue knowledge and other academic pursuits. Given the importance of an educated population in today's society and the converging effects of globalisation, it is

the purpose of every college to generate well-educated students who pursue higher education.

Through flexible preparatory programmes, libraries should provide resources and facilities that can adequately prepare all students for graduation or higher education. The library should be a place where students can enter the higher education field and be a hub of tremendous potential for pursuing higher education with a wealth of resources, facilities, and services. Quality information sources should be available in libraries to help students and their communities prepare for academic pursuits and provide avenues toward holistic development. A library is a person's spiritual home or temple that has a major bearing on their education, future, empowerment, and personal growth. Libraries should be well-stocked with

excellent materials and offer welcoming amenities and services to have an impact on students and their communities by raising students' potential and assisting with their future goals. Libraries should have study areas to help students who don't have access to those chances advance their technical and creative skills and explore career options.

In the aforementioned framework, the current study has investigated the information sources and services stored in the autonomous college libraries of Rayat Shikshan Sanstha in Satara City. The researcher felt the need to determine the types of concerns users encounter, the library's intended use, and the extent to which users are satisfied, in regards to matters such as whether the library has debates, book talks, liberal arts education programmes, or offers users vocational training.

Libraries are described as structured collections of printed and unprinted books and audio visual resources with the assistance of employees who are able to offer and interpret such material as needed, to suit the informational, educational, and leisure needs of their users. Libraries are thought of as organisations that select, acquire, organise, conserve, and make available to those in need sources of information of collected knowledge and experiences. Libraries are crucial resources for education at all levels. It serves as the social and intellectual hub of the community, housing not only academic but also cultural, economic, and social preferences. Users of libraries are exposed to various types of information with various values due to the availability of a wide range of information sources. Additionally, they provide users with the chance to learn and keep learning all throughout their lives.

Libraries are built for the purpose of methodically gathering, organising, preserving, and disseminating knowledge and information. Because we desire to pass on our knowledge and wisdom to future generations, it is crucial for man to preserve and retain the valuable knowledge and information found in books and records. This knowledge can be made available to others so they can profit from it by keeping the documents in a library.

Rayat Shikshan Sanstha:

One of the leading educational institutions in Asia is the Rayat Shikshan Sanstha. In 1919, Dr. Karamaveer Bhaurao Patil founded the Rayat Shikshan Sanstha by establishing a boarding house in Kale (Tal-Karad, Dist-Satara), where he understood that the only way to address social evils was by educating the general populace. However, he quickly moved the administrative offices of his educational school to Satara in 1924.

The Rayat Shikshan Sanstha's four-story central office, which is spread out across an area of around 40469 square metres (4 hectares) and has the mediaeval fort of Ajinkya Tara in the background, directs and regulates the operations of its 709 branches dispersed throughout Maharashtra. The Shahu Boarding House No. 1 and Ismail Sahib Mullah Law Colleges, the Maharaja Sayajirao High School, the Savitribai Phule Mahila Mahavidyalaya, the Mahatma Phule Training College for Men, the Jijamata Training College for Women, and the Bhimabai Ambedkar High School are all located on the campus.

After the death of the original father, Sanstha has become increasingly successful. Like the benign banyan tree, its network of branches has grown far. It currently operates 42 colleges, 444

secondary schools, 7 training colleges, 62 elementary schools (English medium-28), 47 pre-primary schools (English medium-29), 91 hostels, 7 administrative offices, 8 ashramshalas, 3 I.T.I., 57 auxiliary branches, and Research Intitute 1, for a total of 769. Such a dedicated educational institution with 12,965 (female 3881) employees from 171 castes and communities and 4 lakh 44 thousand 135 pupils can only be found in around 15 districts of Maharashtra and one district of Karnataka. The statistics speak of the phenomenal progress and achievement of the Rayat Shikshan Sanstha as dreamt by the Karmaveer.

Definitional Analysis:

- **Use:** The meaning of Use is to cause to act observe for a purpose or as an instrument or as material for consumption. *Oxford dictionary*.
- **Library** - “Library is a collection of books and other literature material kept for Reading, study and consultation”.
- “A collection of films, photographs and other non-book materials, plastic or metal tapes and disks, computer tapes, disks and programs. All of these, as well as printed and manuscript documents, may be provided in departments of one large library or they may be in collections restricted to one type of material. *Harrods’slibrarian’s glossary and reference book*
- **Library - According to Dr. S.R. Ranganathan, Father of library science,** defines the term Library “A library is a public institution of establishment charged with the care of a collection of books and the duty of making them accessible to those who require use them and the task of converting every person in its

neighbourhood into a habitual library goers and a regular reader”.

- **Resources - According to Oxford dictionary,** the meaning of resource is “available assets”.
- **Library Resources: - According to Wikipedia.com,** Library resources are basically sources of information. Traditionally, these resources were mostly books, journals, newspapers and other editorials, and encyclopaedias. But with the advent of the internet, digital sources of information have become prevalentl.
- **Services: - According to oxford dictionary,**
 1. The occupation or process of working for users or of assisting another person or persons.
 2. A system or arrangement that performs work for users or supplies user needs.
- **College Library:**

A college is considered as an academic institution of higher learning offering three-year degree courses. In colleges, the library occupies a prominent position and it is an important and integral part of the teaching programme. It is not merely a depository of books, but an active workshop instrument in the production of or original thinking. The aim of college education and college libraries in inter-related. College library extends opportunities for self-education to the deserving and enthusiastic students without any distinction. These libraries develop in each student a sense of responsibility in the pursuit of knowledge. College library stimulates the students to obtain, evaluate and recognize knowledge and to familiarize themselves with the trends of knowledge for further education and learning new disciplines.
- **Information services: According to Harrods’s librarians glossary and**

reference book “A services provided by, or for, a special library which draws attention to information possessed in the library or information department in anticipation of demand.

- **An Autonomous College:**

As per the rules and standards of the National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC), any college having a score of 3.51 or above on a measurement scale of 0 to 4 is considered as the Autonomous college. The colleges which have a score of 750 or above duly certified by the National Accreditation Board (NAB) is eligible for the rank of the autonomous college. An autonomous college enjoys a couple of good benefits.

Autonomous colleges appoint their Professors, Lecturers, and Faculty. Hence students can have richer conversations with their faculty. Faculty won't keep changing and they will be serving the institution for years together. Hence student-faculty bonds would be better. Exams are being held within the college hence students can gain better access to their faculty. Also, the live interactive sessions are being held with the utmost care and conviction.

Data Analysis:

The majority of the respondents to the structured questionnaires used for the data analysis are drawn from a range of levels, and they cover a variety of topics. The following data analysis is done with respect to the study's stated objectives: The user study was carried out in Satara City's Rayat Shikshan Sanstha Autonomous Colleges. For the users' study, a total of 3 colleges in Satara City were identified.

Frequency to Visit the Library:

Information is the essential element for progress of higher education and plays vital role in national progress. Proper use of information is directly related to the growth of study, research and teaching facilities and its multidirectional growth of higher education. The use of library could be measured in various ways. One such way, which may give an idea of the use of the library, is that of finding the frequency of the visits of users to the library. Frequency of use of a library is an important indicator of its relative importance in terms of its resources and services. Therefore, users frequency of visit has been taken into account to find the use of the library.

Sr. No	Name of College	Frequency					
		Daily	Three times in a week	Twice in a week	Once in a week	Rarely	Total
1	YCIS	15 (42.85%)	7 (20%)	5 (14.28%)	5 (14.28%)	3 (8.57%)	35 (100%)
2	CSC	16 (45.71%)	8 (22.85%)	5 (14.28%)	4 (11.42%)	2 (5.71%)	35 (100%)
3	DGCC	12 (40%)	7 (23.33%)	5 (16.66%)	4 (13.33%)	2 (6.66%)	30 (100%)
Total		43	22	15	13	7	100
Percentage		43%	22%	15%	13%	7%	100%

To analyze the use pattern of users in the library, it is pertinent to study the

frequency of visit, the results of which is given in Table 4.2.2.2 shows that 43% of

users who daily visit the library, 22% of users visit the library three times in a week, 15% of users were visit the library twice in a week, 13% of users visit the library once in a week and 7% of users rarely visit the library. It is clear that, the majority of all the users that they visit the library daily.

43 users daily visit the library. So, it can be said that they come for borrowing reference books or accessing e-resources or for reading purpose. It is seen that they are regular and sincere in their studies. They come to access electronic resources. Rarely use library, users may not regular in the college also and may be they study at home.

Purpose of Visit the Library:

Sl. No	Purpose	☐ (Tick)		
		YCIS	CSC	DGCC
A	Research purpose	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B	To prepare seminar presentation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
C	For writing assignment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
D	To borrow books	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
E	For examination purpose	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
F	For literature search	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
G	Teaching purpose	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
H	To read newspapers/magazines	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I	For browsing	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
J	For reference	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
K	Update knowledge	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Library is peace place where the students can study more rather than any other place. The majority to purpose of visit the library is observed from the table 4.2.2.3 that almost all the college library users they visit the library. So, it can be said that they come to visit for their

Research purpose, to prepare seminar presentation, for writing assignment, to borrow books, for examination purpose, for literature search, Teaching purpose, to read newspapers/magazines, for browsing, For reference and Update knowledge.

Frequency of use of Information Sources

Sl. No	Source	Frequency											
		YCIS				CSC				DGCC			
		4	3	2	1	4	3	2	1	4	3	2	1
A	Text/subject books	4				4				4			
B	Reference books	4				4				4			
C	Reference materials (encyclopaedia, dictionaries, directories etc)			2				2				2	
D	Print journals		3				3				3		
E	Newspapers/Magazines			2				2				2	

(Keyword 4=Great extend, 3=Moderate extend, 2=some extend, 1=can't say)

It is pertinent to study the frequency of use of information sources, the results of which is given in Table 4.2.2.4 shows that there is a great extent of YCIS, CSC and DGCC library users regarding use of information sources like

Text/Subject Books and Reference books. Moderate extent from all library users to print journals and Some extent from all library users regarding reference material and Newspapers/Magazines.

Services to use most in the Library:

Sr. No.	Types of information materials	Services to use most in the library											
		YCIS				CSC				DGCC			
		4	3	2	1	4	3	2	1	4	3	2	1
A	Book loan services	4				4				4			
B	Photocopy services			2				2				2	
C	Current awareness services		3					3				3	
D	Indexing and Abstracting service				1				1				1
E	Selective dissemination of information (SDI)			2				2				2	
F	Digital lab service		3					2				2	
G	OPAC	4				4				4			
H	Oral information/ Reference queries Services			2				2				2	
I	Internet service	4				4				4			

(Keyword 4=Great extend, 3=Moderate extend, 2=some extend, 1=can't say)

The majority to mostly use the services provided by all the libraries is observed from the table 4.2.2.5 that almost all the college library users they mostly use the Book loan services, OPAC, Internet services provided by the libraries. Moderate extent regarding the current awareness services, some extent about photocopy, SDI and oral information provided by the libraries.

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